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An Inquiry into the Continuing Professional Development Training Needs of Education Graduates in a State University in the Philippines

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Abstract

Objectives/Methods: This study adopted a descriptive method of research using a self-administered research instrument to collect data from eighty (80) professional teachers who were purposively sampled among the graduates of Eastern Samar State University- College of Education from School Years 2008-2018 aimed to inquire into the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Training Needs of the respondents. Specifically, it delved to identify the extent of felt need for CPD training in the seven (7) Domains of Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), determine respondents' level of agreement on the benefits from CPD training and determine their preference on CPD training specifications. **Results and Findings:** This study disclosed the intense need of education graduates who are now professional teachers for relevant trainings with a Grand Mean of 3.9 (Much Needed Training) based on PPST. Meanwhile, the desires were centered on Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Understanding the Diversity of Learners and on Curriculum and Planning. It is confirmed that teachers are deeply grounded on the belief that CPD Program is beneficial in the pursuit of their careers as it garnered an overall rating of 4.4 (Much Agreeable) On the CPD training specifications, majority expressed their concern on Trainers' Ideal Characteristics specifically having a deep knowledge on the topic with the highest mean of 4.39 and Paper and Pencil Training Assessment as the most preferred mode with a mean of 3.79. These are vital indicators to measure the success of one's attendance and participation in professional development undertakings. **Novelty:** A "Need -Based Teacher Training cum Continuing Professional Developmental (CPD) Framework " will be instituted based on the findings of the study and can be adopted by ESSU -College of Education or by any Teacher Training Institution in local or global setting towards a sustainable development in the assimilation and practice of Teaching Profession.

Keywords: Inquiry; Continuing Professional Development; Training Needs; Education Graduate

1 Introduction

Continuing Professional Development (CPD) of teachers has been considered as a major key element to enhance quality of instructional delivery at all levels of education and an important area that is of growing interest internationally. It supports the importance of transformational growth approach to teachers' professional development. Hence, there is a need to incorporate richer CPD offering that deals with teachers' professional development needs⁽¹⁾. The overall importance of CPD is to improve teacher effectiveness in the classroom, which in turn helps students reach higher levels of learning. It aims to improve teachers' knowledge, abilities, and attitudes over the course of their careers, with a focus on the local environment, especially classroom practices⁽²⁾.

Strengthening of all policies and strategies on the implementation of CPD should be enhanced and should not be taken-for-granted in order to maintain teachers' competencies. Teachers are to engage in CPD where their learning went beyond the specific in-service activities into a larger and varied curriculum for training and seminar possibilities that help them promote collaborative learning to develop and build their own knowledge, skills, attitude, and values toward professional expansion and development⁽³⁾.

In the Philippines, Continuing Professional Development Act of 2016 is instituted to improve the competence of Filipino professionals and make them attuned to the development and advancements in their chosen field. Specifically, the Philippine Regulatory Commission (PRC) is requiring all Professional Teachers to complete 45 credit units to renew their license in a period of time to update their competence aligned with Philippine Qualification Framework (PQF)⁽⁴⁾ and The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) with applicable pedagogical trends applicable in the local and global practice of the profession⁽⁵⁾. Moreover, professional development can be made available within institutions or through external providers, such as training institutes and higher education institutions⁽⁶⁾.

The increased attention on CPD by the Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs), like the Eastern Samar State University (ESSU)-College of Education is partly subsequent to changes in delivery and monitoring formats following global competitions (i.e. PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS), where countries are competing on a global knowledge market. To meet downward student performance, there seems to be an unproblematic conviction that if only teachers' professional skills and knowledge are enhanced the students will perform better⁽⁷⁾.

Corollary to the emerging contexts and the challenges, ESSU-College of Education which primarily produces majority of professional teachers in the province and even other TEIs would pose questions on how to make the CPD Programs relevant and richer. Would a bottom-up model be appropriate analyzing the current professional needs of teachers in their professional development? How would the TEIs as CPD Providers create an instructional design for teachers that would address their training needs?

Undoubtedly, stakeholders of educational system and policymakers are increasingly looking to teacher professional trainings as an important strategy for supporting the complex skills students need to be prepared for further education and work in the 21st century⁽⁸⁾. As such, crafting CPD Programs at the local level would be very essential for TEIs. As cited, local CPD practices seem to be part of a broader reskilling of the teachers' workforce⁽⁹⁾.

Previous studies viewed CPDs in different perspectives. As cited in one of the studies that some teachers were not in-favor of the CPD implementation in the country as they are self-directed and autonomous and lifelong learner-professionals⁽¹⁰⁾. However, there are wide range of international literature, together with some specific examples in proposing a framework built around key characteristics of individual models of CPD.⁽¹¹⁾ It is noted, that one of the driving factors for the implementation of teacher professional development is on the readiness of teachers to be fostered and good cooperation between teachers and principals⁽¹²⁾. As reviewed, there is a dearth of literature and studies looking into the training needs of teachers and addressing them through relevant CPD trainings and programs.

Having considered this educational milieu in seeking to achieve transformational professional development, it is important to recognize teachers' voices and views in the development of CPD Programs through an inquiry process. As observed, much is already demanded from teachers to maintain subject area knowledge and the skills for teaching that content in a rapidly changing world, while providing instruction that is responsive to the diverse needs of their students and communities⁽¹³⁾. This paper aims to capture insightful information to the continuing quest for pedagogical innovations from professional teachers that are responsive to the Philippines and international standards as reflected in the PPST.

It is in this light that TEIs in State Universities in the Philippines like Eastern Samar State University (ESSU) and all other Teacher Training Institutions in the world need to be proactive in the formulation of a "Need -Based Teacher Training cum Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Framework "towards proper assimilation and practice of their profession as this will lead to sustainable development in education.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

A Descriptive research design was adopted for the study as it delved into objective inquiry of the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Training Needs of the Teacher Education Graduates for their professional development and is used to systematically gather information on the important benefits the respondents will derive from the training and describe their preferred training specifications. Moreover, this research design provides a comprehensive picture of the respondents' perspectives in gaining a deeper understanding on how a Need-Based Teacher Training CPD Framework will be instituted.

2.2 Respondents of the Study

This study involved eighty (80) respondents who were purposively sampled among the professional teachers who were graduates of Eastern Samar State University from school years 2008-2018. They were carefully selected based as they can best supply the needed information as they were already occupying permanent teaching positions in the different schools in the Division of Eastern Samar.

2.3 Research Instrument

A self-administered survey research instrument was used to collect data from the respondents. The items for the training needs were taken based from the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). The PPST is a public statement of what teachers need to know, value, and be able to do in their practice. The seven Domains of PPST were integrated in the research instrument to identify the areas of their training needs: (1) Content Knowledge and Pedagogy; (2) Learning Environment; (3) Diversity of Learners; (4) Curriculum and Planning; (5) Assessment and Reporting; (6) Community Linkages and Professional Engagement; and (7) Personal Growth and Professional Development. The description of training benefits and training specifications were derived from the revised guidelines on the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Program for all Registered and Licensed Professional issued by Professional Regulation Commission (PRC).

2.4 Analysis of Data

Result of the data gathered was analyzed using the Mean as the major statistical tool. Mean score was obtained to analyze and interpret the data in order to facilitate a scientific inquiry on the CPD Training needs among the respondents. Specifically, it identified the extent of felt need for CPD training of ESSU Education Graduates (professional teachers) in the seven (7) domains in PPST from Much Needed Training to Not Needed Training. It determined the respondents' level of agreement on the benefits they will derive from CPD training from Much Agreeable to Not Agreeable, and determine the participants' responses on their preferred CPD training specifications.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Training Needs of Education Graduates

Table 1. Summary Table on Training Needs of Education Graduates

Criteria	Grand Mean	Interpretation
1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.1	Much Needed Training
2. Learning Environment	3.7	Much Needed Training
3. Diversity of Learners	4.06	Much Needed Training
4. Curriculum and Planning	4.02	Much Needed Training
5. Assessment and Reporting	3.7	Much Needed Training
6. Community Linkage and Professional Development	3.82	Much Needed Training
7. Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.94	Much Needed Training
Average Grand Mean	3.9	Much Needed Training

The data on the table implied that the professional teachers who are Education Graduates need to increase their level of knowledge, practice and professional engagement for them to meet the expectations as stipulated in the Philippine Professional

Standards for Teachers and to achieve the quality needed in the assimilation and practice of their profession.

Specifically, the need to be trained on Content Knowledge and Pedagogy gets the highest mean which is consistent to the interesting findings that teachers need to be better prepared to cope with the daunting sustainability challenges in the way instructional delivery are to be provided to the students in the K to 12 Program⁽¹⁴⁾. Training on Content Knowledge and Pedagogy are conducted to upgrade the teacher educators in their specialization in terms of knowledge of the latest developments, current issues, and their trends and application and their relevance to teaching.

The findings is related to the study that teachers’ training revolves on enhancing pedagogical skills that includes training about information, communication and technology (ICT) integration as these are essential skills for teachers to create a new learning environment responsive to the needs of the 21st century learners⁽¹⁵⁾.

3.2 Respondents’ Perception on the Benefits derive from CPD Training

Table 2. Respondents’ Perception on the Benefits derive from CPD Training

Criteria	Mean	Interpretation
1. CPD allows me to extend the depth of my knowledge and understanding into related and new fields that will benefit my current role as a teacher	4.3	Much Agreeable
2. CPD ensures me to develop and enhance the knowledge, understanding and skills I need to deliver as a professional teacher to my students/pupils, clients and those I engage with my professional capacity.	4.3	Much Agreeable
3. CPD ensures my capabilities to keep pace with the current teaching standards and hopefully advance and progress my teaching skills further thus allowing me to become an asset to my school where I am connected.	4.4	Much Agreeable
4. CPD ensures that my knowledge stay relevant and up to date at all times on current trends in teaching/pedagogy and I will become more aware of the changing trends and directions in my profession and are comfortable discussing current practices with my co-teachers.	4.4	Much Agreeable
5. CPD can lead me into a deeper understanding of what it means to be a professional teacher , along with a greater appreciation of the implications and impacts of my work as a teacher.	4.6	Very Much Agreeable
6. CPD will provide me the opportunity to engage and learn from others in my own field of specialization by interaction and idea sharing at events, by attending courses and online discussion.	4.3	Much Agreeable
7. CPD allows me to hone and fine tune existing teaching/ pedagogical skills, develop new ones and also helps me fill and skills gaps.	4.2	Much Agreeable
8. CPD is recognized by PRC and other professional membership bodies and organizations and will assist me in building my reputation for all the right reasons including the renewal of my teacher’s license.	4.2	Much Agreeable
9. CPD helps me to understand the theory behind the practical application (and vice versa).	4.3	Much Agreeable
10. CPD today is viewed by employers as one of the most important aspects of an individual’s career and should be taken very seriously for promotion to a higher rank	4.4	Much Agreeable
Grand Mean	4.4	Much Agreeable

The respondents were much agreeable on all the items used to measure their perceptions on the benefits they will derive from the CPD trainings to further enhance their pedagogical competence and translate them into real practice of their teaching profession in their respective field of assignments. With the highest mean (4.6 , the professional teachers believed that CPD can lead them into a deeper understanding of what it means to be professional teachers , along with a greater appreciation of the implications and impacts of their work as a teacher. Similarly,

Investigating the impact of CPD, the study concludes that the CPD program supported the development of critically reflective classroom practice, which teacher participants believe have led to an improvement in pupils’ learning. Significantly, CPD activities enhance teachers’ personal competencies, improving teaching and learning process and improving learner outcomes. Thus, the school heads should empower teachers’ engagement in CPD activities⁽¹⁶⁾.

3.3 Respondents' Identified Trainer's Characteristics

Table 3. Respondents' Preferred CPD Training in Relation to Trainer's Characteristics

Criteria	Mean	Interpretation
1. Has deep knowledge about the Topic	4.5	Very Much Preferred
2. Has a command of the learning material	4.4	Much Preferred
3. Has rhythm and energy.	4.3	Much Preferred
4. Has the power to interact with the participants	4.42	Much Preferred
5. Has innate creativity	4.35	Much Preferred

The table revealed that the respondents' preferred CPD trainers who have deep knowledge about the topic with a mean of 4.5 (Very much preferred). Respondents expressed their preferred characteristics of a Trainers as they will be leading and nurturing them in the process of learning new skills in teaching. In contrast, in a study, CPD was not making the most effective use of it. The teachers associated it with other issues often unrelated to the purposes of CPD. Emphasis on generic contents of training materials, lack of ownership, inconsistencies on its provision, disparity of knowledge among teachers, and supervisors and principals, and conceptual problems about CPD were among the identified factors that hindered its effective implementation⁽¹⁷⁾. Meanwhile, this paper attempted to identify trainers' characteristics with an end view of making this as basis in the selection of trainers in the conduct of CPD Program for teachers.

3.4 Respondents' Preferred CPD Training Specifications

Summary Table on Respondents' CPD Training Preferences with Highest

Table 4. Summary Table on Respondents' CPD Training Preferences with Highest Mean

Criteria		Mean	Interpretation
Training Modality	Face-to-Face	4.02	Much Preferred
Training Venue	On-Campus	3.95	Much Preferred
Training Cost, Inclusion & Duration	Php2,000-3000 Registration for 2-day CPD Training with lunch per day	3.3	Preferred
Training Assessment	Paper and Pencil Test	3.79	Much Preferred

The table presents the CPD Training Specification that are considered by the respondents:. Face-to-Face Modality, On-Campus Training, Training Cost and Duration of Training and the conventional paper and pencil training Assessment

Seemingly, this paper is to some extent different on the respondents' preferred face-to-face training modality as compared to the study of Okada⁽¹⁸⁾. Teacher Training for Professional Education was done through a Course Extension with Emerging Technologies in Open Schooling as the advanced technology that the respondents have in their training engagement context was considered.

For TEIs which are proactively responding to the challenge of becoming CPD Providers may consider the data in the preparation of CPD Instructional Plan and in framing the CPD Framework for Teachers' Training.

4 Conclusion

It is confirmed in this study that teachers have training needs and deeply grounded on the belief that CPD Program as set by PRC for the renewal of professional license as a major key element to enhance their teaching profession. As such, the benefits that they will derive from the CPD Trainings ensure personal growth and professional development as these are leading them into a deeper understanding of what it means to be professional teachers , along with a greater appreciation of the implications and impacts of their work

On the CPD training specifications, majority expressed their concern on the Trainers' Characteristics and Training Assessment as these are vital indicators to measure the success of one's attendance and participation in professional development. These findings will be a strong basis in the systematic formulation of a "Need-Based Teacher Training cum CPD Framework" to be provided by ESSU and other TEIs in the Philippines and in other countries.

4.1 Recommendation

A “Need –Based Teacher Training cum Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Framework “ will be instituted based on the findings of the study and can be adopted by ESSU –College of Education or by any Teacher Training Institution in local or global setting towards the attainment of the sustainable goals in the provision of quality education and lifelong learning for all. Hence, an objective validation and impact assessment need to be explored through a phenomenological study using narratives of teachers’ professional development.

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